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POLITICS AND LAW: PROBLEMS OF INTERACTION

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ANNOTATION

The article discusses the point that both politics and law are associated with the existence of state institutions. Numerous theoretical concepts of politics directly or indirectly single out the state and political power as its central point. Linking politics with its substantial essence - power, we can say that in a democracy, political power is not reduced to state power. State power has clear features: sovereignty, territory, population, a number of monopolies (for issuing laws, for coercion, collecting taxes). Political power is dispersed throughout society, as there are many centers of interest and political influence. This is possible due to the presence and guarantee of political rights and freedoms.

Keywords: politics, law, interaction, society, coercion, sovereignty, state power, political power.

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ПОЛИТИКА И ПРАВО: ПРОБЛЕМЫ ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье уточняется тот момент, что и политика, и право связаны с существованием государственных институтов. Многочисленные теоретические концепции политики прямо или косвенно её центральным пунктом выделяют государство и политическую власть. Связывая политику с её субстанциональной сущностью – властью, можно сказать, что в условиях демократии политическая власть не сводится к власти государственной. Государственная власть обладает четкими признаками:

суверенитет, территория, население, ряд монополий (на издание законов, на принуждение, сбор налогов). Политическая власть рассредоточена в обществе, так как существует много центров интересов и политического влияния. Это возможно благодаря наличию и гарантии политических прав и свобод.

Ключевые слова: политика, право, взаимодействие, общество, принуждение, суверенитет, государственная власть, политическая власть.

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SIYOSAT VA HUQUQ: O'ZARO MUNOSABATLAR MUAMMOLARI

ANNOTASIYA

Ushbu maqolada siyosat ham, huquq ham davlat institutlarining mavjudligi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan nuqta ko'rsatilgan. Siyosatning ko'plab nazariy tushunchalari to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yoki bilvosita uning Markaziy nuqtasi bilan davlat va siyosiy hokimiyatni ajratib turadi. Siyosatni uning muhim mohiyati – kuchi bilan bog'lab, aytishimiz mumkinki, demokratiyada siyosiy hokimiyat davlat hokimiyatiga kamaytirilmaydi. Davlat hokimiyati aniq xususiyatlarga ega: suverenitet, hudud, aholi, bir qator monopoliyalar (qonunlarni nashr etish, majburlash, soliq yig'ish). Siyosiy hokimiyat jamiyatda tarqalib ketgan, chunki ko'plab qiziqish va siyosiy ta'sir markazlari mavjud. Bu siyosiy huquq va erkinliklarning mavjudligi va kafolati tufayli mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: siyosat, huquq, o'zaro ta'sir, jamiyat, majburlash, suverenitet, davlat hokimiyati, siyosiy hokimiyat.

The problem of interaction between politics and law is a hot topic of modern scientific and educational literature. However, it acts as a "secondary actor", a background for considering either issues of legal regulation of social relations, or for considering the political process. Empirically verified mechanisms and procedures for the interaction of these essential regulatory spheres of social life in modern literature have not yet been sufficiently studied.

Among the key works devoted to the problem of interaction between politics and law, one can single out the monograph by A.S. Avtonomov "Legal ontology of politics: towards the construction of a system of categories", works by V.S. Nersesyants "Philosophy of Law", "Law as a Necessary Form of Equality, Freedom and Justice", monograph by G.A. Vasilevich "State authorities in the Republic of Belarus (constitutional and legal status)". The interaction of politics and law was studied in the works of such authors as S.S. Alekseev, L.N. Zavadskaya, V.V. Lazarev, G.V. Maltsev, M.N. Marchenko, L.A. Morozova, E.Yu. Solovyov, L.S. Yavich and others. Since 1999, the scientific journal "Law and Politics" has been published in the Russian Federation. The monograph by S.A. Egorov "Political jurisprudence in the USA". S.A. Egorov writes about "political jurisprudence" as an interdisciplinary area of legal and political science. His study of the judiciary is an example of a political science approach to law. In the legal science of the United States, a theory of "political jurisprudence" has developed, which is based on realism and behaviorism in law. This theory is focused not so much on the analysis of formal legal constructions as on the analysis of actual behavior in the right sphere. Egorov S.A. notes that political jurisprudence had the greatest influence on the sciences of constitutional and administrative law. Within the framework of this theory, law "legally formalizes and consolidates the political system, structure, formation procedure and competence of public authorities, the rights and freedoms of citizens, streamlines and regulates the process of public administration ... The legal system is considered as a set of ordered legal means and institutions for resolving disputes in the state » [1, p.9-10].

A realistic approach to the study of state and law in the United States appeared thanks to the concept of the state by A. Bentley, known as the creator of the theory of interest groups. The behavioral approach considers law as an institution for meeting social needs through the regulation of political behavior within a politically organized community (R. Pound). It should be noted that representatives of these areas reduce to a minimum the normative and prescriptive element in law. [2, p.96].

"Political jurisprudence" is close in essence to the understanding of law to the *sociological school*, in which law is understood as a system of legal relations, the behavior of people in the field of law: "law is a system of regulation of social relations, expressed in official sources, which is

characterized by formal certainty based on ideas justice and freedom, ensuring the interests of the individual, society and the state. [3, p.8-9].

In order to identify the mechanisms of interaction between law and politics, let us dwell on the essential characteristics of each of the phenomena.

Law is a system of state-sanctioned, generally binding, formally defined rules of a general nature (norms) provided with state protection. Law is “a set of generally binding, formally defined norms emanating from the state, expressing the ideas of freedom, justice, humanism, morality, human rights and designed to *regulate* the behavior of people and their teams in order to ensure the stable functioning and development of society” [4, p. 265].

Law is called upon to ensure formal equality, a universal and necessary form of freedom, justice. The main characteristics of law include normativity, obligatory nature, state nature, formalization, state protection, systemicity.

Normativity means that law is a system of norms that define the most general, typical models of behavior. Legal norms are the scale of lawful behavior. The normativity of law is due to the typicality, homogeneity, mass character, repetition of individual social situations, phenomena, and interactions. The addressees of the normative rules are not specific subjects listed by name, but homogeneous categories of persons. Thus, the law regulates the behavior of a personally indefinite circle of persons, operates continuously (permanently, until the abolition or change of the relevant legal norm.)

Obligatory nature means that the law regulates the behavior of each person in a normatively prescribed situation. The law is universal in nature, extending its effect to the entire territory of the country, to all its population. At the same time, legal norms are binding on everyone, including the state. Imperative, binding law does not depend on the discretion or consent of individuals to submit to legal influence. The obligatory nature of law creates the basis for the formal legal equality of subjects before the law and the court, for the elimination of any discrimination. Law in its essence is the same "rules of the game" for all. As a result, elements of justice, unity, and equality are introduced into public life.

Formalization - law is characterized by documentary fixation of norms in certain sources, adopted according to the established procedure. Rules of law are always outwardly expressed (objectified) and fixed materially. Procedural (procedural) aspects in jurisprudence are of great importance. An unpublished law is not applicable. A norm that is not brought to the public attention does not give rise to legal consequences. Thus, law is characterized by public perception.

state nature. Law comes directly from the state. Thus, the law is given an official, public character. The norms of law are formed as a result of purposeful law-making activity, which is an attribute of the state. A special role in the activities of the state and its bodies is played by such branches of law as constitutional and administrative law.

Legal norms are sanctioned by the state, but in certain periods of time they depend on the alignment of political forces. As Doctor of Law, Professor M.N. Marchenko, “historical experience shows that the form of the state, this or that state body and its activities can be somewhat stable, effective and enjoy the trust of society if they are legally formalized and secured. This equally applies to political parties, organizations, social movements (in any case, the fundamental aspects of their activities - program goals, procedures for creating and terminating the existence of finances, property, participation in election campaigns, etc.). [...] In turn, law is most directly based on political (not only state) institutions. Political nature, political properties are more or less characteristic of all legal phenomena” [5, p. 522-523].

The state reveals the political, economic, social claims of certain groups, sections of the population, and then forms and elevates into law a kind of coordinated will of society.

State protection - this sign follows from the universal validity of law and complements it. While moral, corporate, customary, religious and other social norms are supported by public sanctions, the right is protected and guaranteed by the state. If necessary, law and order is provided by state coercion, “legalized violence”.

Consistency - law is an integral system of norms, an organized set of structural elements,

interconnected and interacting in a certain way. In general, law must have internal unity, consistency.

Law, like the state, is characterized by a dual nature. The dualism of law is manifested in the combination of social group and general social components. On the one hand, law expresses the will of the ruling elite, on the other hand, the long-term interests of the whole society. *The social and group* component lies in the fact that the groupings in power have the opportunity to influence the processes of lawmaking for their own, corporate purposes. Law in the hands of the ruling elite can become a means of forming, implementing and protecting narrow group interests. The general *social component* shows that in any state law is not only a narrow class or group instrument, but also an expression of a compromise *between different social groups*. In a democratic society, law is a product of social consent.

It should be noted that law and legislation are not identical concepts. Only a law that corresponds to democratic legal ideas, principles, values, inalienable rights and freedoms of a person is legal. The essence of modern law is the objectively conditioned and normatively fixed common will of all members of society as a result of the coordination of individual and collective interests on fundamental, long-term issues of the life of society and the state. [6, p.174]

The very essence of law as a regulator of special social relations connects it not only with state institutions, but also with the political process in a broader sense of the word, since the coordination of group interests is the core of the political process. Politics can be considered 1) as a sphere of public life; 2) as one of the types of social activity (political activity) and a type of social relations; 3) as the art of conquest of power, its retention; 4) as the art of finding a balance of interests, the art of government and as a science.

It is also helpful to understand the interaction between law and politics by highlighting the three dimensions of politics – formal, substantive and procedural.

The formal dimension of politics (Polity) is political institutions whose activities are fixed by legal norms and political traditions. It is the institutional framework for political activity and human behavior. The formal dimension of politics studies the political organization of society, the state and other political institutions, organizational and legal norms that give stability and stability to politics and allow regulating the political behavior of people. Polity is the political system of society, fixed in a constitutional way.

The meaningful dimension of politics (Policy) is a political course that is associated with specific public interests, value orientations, and technologies for making political decisions. The substantive dimension of politics is related to the activities of the state and social groups in solving significant social problems (for example, economic policy, policy in the field of education, health care, etc.). The content dimension is supplemented by the concept of Public Policy - the sphere of political management, controlled by the public.

The procedural dimension (Politics) reflects specific political processes that have volitional, intellectual, socio-psychological forms. The political process is often compared to a "struggle for power". Politics is actually a political sphere [7, p. eight].

So, the formal dimension of politics is concentrated in the concept of "constitutional system". The meaningful dimension of politics is connected with the implementation of the political course. Accordingly, at this level, political decisions are clothed in a legal form and concentrated in legal acts subordinate to the constitution and laws (government decrees; acts of ministries and state committees; decisions of local councils, executive and administrative authorities). The implementation of the political course is ensured by the norms of administrative law.

The first two levels of policy (formal and substantive) carry elements of stability to a greater extent than volatility. The procedural dimension of politics, unlike the first two, is actually connected with the "element of the struggle for power." At this level of policy implementation, the norms of the electoral law, constitutionally enshrined and explained in the relevant normative acts, political rights, are of key importance. However, it should be remembered that the policy is implemented not only with the help of law. Other means include diplomatic and military actions, agitation, propaganda, acts of disobedience and protest. The procedural dimension of politics is not rigidly formalized, but provides the basis for the institutionalization of certain social practices in the form of legal norms.

So, politics is a dynamic phenomenon, in the modern world it has a procedural character. This is the process of preparation, adoption and implementation of decisions binding on the whole society. In the political process, development goals are defined, decisions are made; there is a mobilization of resources and organization of the masses to achieve the set goals, political activity is regulated, the results obtained are monitored and analyzed, new policy goals are determined. Formal and substantive changes in policy are closely related to state power and reflect its stability. The formal dimension of politics clearly reflects its constitutional and legal basis. However, the foundations of the state system are also undergoing changes, not to mention the configuration of individual political institutions. These changes are influenced by the procedural level of the policy. In general, the political system acts as a mechanism that ensures the connection between society and state institutions.

For the study of the relationship between politics and law, a significant fact is that the modern understanding of democracy, *the allocation of signs of a democratic political regime almost completely coincides with the signs of a rule of law state* (the inviolability of the freedom of the individual, his rights, honor and dignity; mutual responsibility of the state and the individual; the rule of law; universality rights, bound by the law of the state itself and its bodies; separation of powers; electability and periodic replacement of government bodies; the existence of effective forms of control and supervision over the observance of the rights and freedoms of citizens). Real democracy and the rule of law presuppose the separation of powers not only vertically, but also horizontally, the existence of mechanisms for tapping the potential of society through self-government. This is linked to a multi-level understanding of the essence of the policy implemented both at the macro and micro levels. Law regulates social relations in the most diverse areas of human activity, the most diverse subjects of law, on various factual grounds. Politics acts as an organizational and regulatory-control sphere of society, which is due to its properties such as universality, all-encompassing nature, inclusiveness (involvement in all spheres), and the ability to influence almost any aspect of life. The functionality of politics not only allows it to deeply influence other areas of public life, but also connects it with them. What unites politics and law? The answer is obvious - they act as regulators of human behavior. Law can be defined through a description of its objective, essential properties: formal equality, a universal and necessary form of freedom, justice. All these essential properties apply to politics as well. Citizens evaluate the activities of the state rather than from a purely *legal point* of view, but from a political and legal point of view, focusing precisely on the observance of the principles of equality, freedom and justice.

Both politics and law are linked to the existence of state institutions. Numerous theoretical concepts of politics directly or indirectly single out the state and political power as its central point. However, while law is a set of norms protected by the state, politics is dispersed in society, constantly produced by the activities of various social groups. Linking politics with its substantial essence - power, we can say that in a democracy, political power is not reduced to state power. State power has clear features: sovereignty, territory, population, a number of monopolies (for issuing laws, for coercion, collecting taxes). Political power is dispersed throughout society, as there are many centers of interest and political influence. This is possible due to the presence and guarantee of political rights and freedoms.

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